

FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF VISCEROPTOSIS IN COMBINATION WITH CHRONIC COLOSTASIS

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Relevance of the Problem. Visceroptosis has several synonyms (enteroptosis, splanchnoptosis, Glenard syndrome; from Greek σπλάγχνα – internal organs and πτώσις – prolapse) [2;4]. According to various researchers, visceroptosis is complicated by chronic colostasis in 30-40% of cases and is one of the common diseases among the working-age population [3]. The prevalence rate is unknown, as the disease presents clinical symptoms in only 10-20% of cases [1].

The aim of the study. To determine the clinical course characteristics of visceroptosis in combination with chronic colostasis.

Materials and Methods. This study was conducted on 132 patients diagnosed with visceroptosis in combination with chronic colostasis (CC), who underwent inpatient treatment at the coloproctology department of the Surgery and Civil Defense Department of the Andijan State Medical Institute Clinic.

Inclusion Criteria: 1. age over 18 years; 2. verified diagnosis of visceroptosis in combination with colostasis (CC); 3. elective nature of the pathology; 4. absence of acute infectious and inflammatory diseases; 5. written consent from the patient and their relatives for examination and treatment.

According to the study's aim and objectives, the patients were conditionally divided into two groups:

- **comparison group** (2018–2022) – 85 patients (64.4%) who underwent a retrospective analysis of surgical treatment outcomes following traditional approaches.

- **main group** (2020–2023) – 47 patients (35.6%) who underwent a prospective study of surgical treatment with an optimized surgical strategy.

To achieve the research objectives, clinical-laboratory, instrumental, and statistical studies were conducted in accordance with the latest standard methodologies recommended by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Results and Discussion: The uniformity of the primary surgical pathology, equal conditions for providing specialized care, the similarity of comorbidities

and their frequency, as well as the nature of surgical interventions, allowed us to present the quantitative characteristics in a consolidated form.

An analysis of the gender distribution of patients with visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis (CC) in elective surgery conditions showed that men accounted for 28 cases (23.3%), while women made up 104 cases (78.8%). Our analysis indicates that visceroptosis combined with chronic CC is predominantly diagnosed in female patients, with an average ratio of 3.7:1. This finding warranted a more detailed investigation of this pattern. Visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis (CC) was most frequently diagnosed in patients aged 45–59 years—67 cases (50.8%). This age group represents the most active working population, which is often exposed to external factors. Among patients aged 18–44 years, visceroptosis with chronic CC was diagnosed in 37 cases (28.0%), mostly associated with congenital developmental anomalies. Patients aged 60 years and older accounted for 28 cases (21.2%), suggesting excessively prolonged conservative treatment. Surgical intervention for visceroptosis with chronic CC was performed in patients with a disease duration of 1–5 years in 42 cases (31.8%), including 37 women (28.9%) and 5 men (3.8%). The disease duration of 6–10 years was observed in 64 patients (48.5%), comprising 47 women (35.6%) and 17 men (12.9%). Particular concern arises for patients with a disease duration of over 10 years—26 cases (19.7%), including 20 women (15.2%) and 6 men (4.5%).

To determine the factors contributing to visceroptosis, we analyzed the body constitution of the studied patients. It is noteworthy that visceroptosis was most frequently diagnosed in patients with an asthenic body type—84 cases (63.6%), including 16 men (12.1%) and 68 women (51.5%). Among patients with a normosthenic body type, the disease was identified in 43 cases (32.6%), with 8 men (6.1%) and 35 women (26.5%). The condition was diagnosed least frequently in patients with a hypersthenic body type—only 5 cases (3.8%), including 4 men (3.0%) and 1 woman (0.8%).

The clinical symptom complex of visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis (CC) consisted of general and local symptoms. Constipation, as the main manifestation of visceroptosis, was observed in 110 patients (83.3%), while alternating constipation and diarrhea occurred in 22 patients (16.7%). A feeling of heaviness in the abdomen was noted in 102 cases (77.3%), intestinal bloating in 89 cases (67.4%), and pain of varying intensity in 127 cases (96.2%). Abdominal sagging and striae were found in 25 patients (18.9%), diastasis of the

anterior abdominal wall muscles in 9 cases (6.8%), and intoxication symptoms (weakness, dizziness, nervousness) in 129 cases (97.7%).

In visceroptosis combined with chronic CC, an analysis of the degree of colonic obstruction was conducted, as unreasonably prolonged conservative treatment worsens patients' conditions, negatively affecting their quality of life. The compensated stage of visceroptosis (constipation lasting less than 3–4 days) was observed in 26 cases (19.7%). The subcompensated stage (constipation lasting 5–10 days) was identified in 61 cases (46.2%), while the decompensated stage (constipation lasting more than 10 days) was detected in 45 cases (34.1%).

Determining the degree of colonic obstruction in visceroptosis was essential for establishing the scope and timing of surgical intervention.

As is well known, comorbid therapeutic conditions significantly influence the choice of surgical tactics and postoperative rehabilitation. Among the studied patients, cardiovascular diseases (ischemic heart disease, hypertension, angina pectoris) were the most frequently diagnosed, occurring in 25 cases (18.9%). Diseases of the hepatobiliary system (type 2 diabetes mellitus, chronic cholecystitis) were identified in 10 cases (7.6%), chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (chronic bronchitis, pneumonia, bronchial asthma) in 8 cases (6.1%), and genitourinary system diseases (chronic pyelonephritis, cystitis) in 11 cases (8.3%).

Severe comorbid therapeutic conditions created additional challenges in determining surgical tactics and postoperative rehabilitation, especially given the initially severe condition of the patients. A history of previous surgical interventions was noted in 58 cases (43.9%) among patients with visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis (CC). Of particular note was the relatively high frequency of cesarean sections—25 cases (18.9%)—as well as surgical interventions for large ventral hernias and diastasis of the anterior abdominal wall muscles in 13 cases (9.8%).

The conducted analysis suggests that multiple pregnancies (cesarean sections) and the presence of large ventral hernias with muscle diastasis play a role in the development and progression of visceroptosis. Additionally, a history of cholecystectomy was recorded in 5 cases (3.8%), appendectomy in 8 cases (6.1%), and hysterectomy with extirpation in 7 cases (5.3%).

Conclusion. The study identified the clinical features of visceroptosis, which include a significant predominance of females, with a male-to-female ratio of 3.7:1, and a high incidence in middle age. Diagnosis at a young age indicates

congenital developmental anomalies, while diagnosis in older patients suggests excessively prolonged conservative treatment, leading to disease progression. The clinical symptom complex consisted of general and local symptoms, with the main manifestations being constipation, alternating constipation and diarrhea, as well as dyspeptic symptoms and signs of intoxication. Comorbid therapeutic conditions were observed in 40.1% of cases, with cardiovascular diseases accounting for the majority (18.9%). The analysis suggests that multiple pregnancies (cesarean section—18.9%) and the presence of large ventral hernias with muscle diastasis (9.8%) play a role in the development and progression of visceroptosis.

Thus, in cases of visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis, considering the clinical course features will allow for the optimization of surgical tactics and improved treatment outcomes.

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